

**AN ANALYSIS OF CODE SWITCHING AND ITS
FREQUENCY IN THE INDONESIAN LOCAL TELEVISION
PROGRAM OF JTV**

“B_CAK SHOW JTV EPS DODIT MULYANTO SEG 5”

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ABSTRACT

Language is the ability to acquire and use complex systems of communication, particularly the human ability to do so, and a language is any specific example of such a system. Language is used by people to make communication to each other. This study will analyze the code switching in communication in a program of Indonesian local television program "B-cak show JTV". In this case the writer analyzed what type of code-switching and its frequency, how many are they used by the host of this program. This research used The data were taken from online video YouTube titled "B-cak show JTV eps Dodit Mulyanto seg 5" which The video-length is 7 minutes and 34 seconds. Then the writer analyzed the video by watching it and taking note from utterances of the host. The research used theory of poplack (1980:230) which code switching divided into three types 1. Inter-sentensial switching, 2. Tag-switching and 3. Intra-sentensial switching.

Keyword: code switching, type, frequency, language, research

A. INTRODUCTION

Language cannot be separated from society's life because it is an essential part of human existence. Language is the ability to acquire and use complex systems of communication, particularly the uniquely human capacity to do so. A language refers to any specific example of such a system. Thus, language is commonly used by people to communicate with one another. According to Shamsuddin (1986:2), language can be understood in two ways. First, language is a tool used to shape thoughts, feelings, desires, and actions, as well as a tool used to influence and be influenced. Second, language is a clear indicator of a person's good or bad character, a reflection of the family and the nation, and an expression of human thought.

In the era of globalization, people increasingly interact with others not only from the same background but also from different ethnic groups and even nationalities. In such cases, people need strategies to solve communication challenges by choosing an appropriate language or code. The use of another language or code in conversation is called code-switching. Code-switching can be defined as the use of more than one language, variety, or style by a speaker within an utterance or discourse, or between different interlocutors or situations (Romaine, 1992:110). Holmes (2001:35) classifies code-switching into two categories: situational and metaphorical. Situational code-switching is identified by the reasons for employing a code switch, whereas metaphorical code-switching occurs without a specific intended meaning (Holmes, 2001:40).

On the other hand, bilingualism and multilingualism have become common phenomena that can be found almost everywhere, including in television programs. Bilingualism refers to the use of two languages, while multilingualism refers to the use of two or more languages, either by an individual speaker or by a community of speakers. According to Nababan (1984:27), bilingualism is the habitual use of two languages in interaction with other people. Bilingualism and multilingualism have become social phenomena shaped by the needs of society and cultural openness. In television media, many presenters or program hosts use more than one language or code in their broadcasts. In this case, they employ code-switching to convey their messages to the viewers

In Indonesia, bilingualism and multilingualism are inseparable, as the country consists of many ethnic groups with different languages and cultures. This condition enables many Indonesians to speak more than one language. Bilingualism and multilingualism are also reflected in television programs, such as the *B-cak Show* on JTV. In this program, the presenters or hosts use three different languages—Javanese, Indonesian, and English—in their interactions.

In this study, the researcher analyzed code-switching in the *B-cak Show* on JTV. Since some readers may not be familiar with this program, it should be explained that the *B-cak Show* is a comedy program in which the announcers or hosts present news in a humorous way. This program aired from 2008 to 2016 on the local Indonesian television channel JTV, whose broadcasting coverage included most areas of East Java Province.

As stated above, Nunan and Carter (2001:275) define code-switching as the phenomenon of switching from one language to another within the same discourse. In the *B-cak Show*, code-switching occurs in the conversations between the host and the guest, where the host switches from Javanese to Indonesian. Sometimes, they also switch from English to Indonesian or Javanese. This practice helps viewers better understand the messages that the hosts intend to deliver in such conversations. Furthermore, code-switching can occur within a single sentence or utterance. Wardhaugh (2005:100) argues that whenever people choose to speak, they may also decide to switch from one code to another, or even mix codes, which sometimes occurs in very short utterances. Thus, speakers can switch codes within only one sentence, which already conveys their intended meaning.

Based on the above explanation and description, code-switching is worth analyzing because it is a phenomenon that affects our daily lives. It is also very interesting to study. On the other hand, the *B-cak Show* is a local comedy program that represents local language use, particularly Javanese as its main language. This not only helps preserve the local language but also provides knowledge that code-switching can happen everywhere and be practiced by anyone.

B. Problem Formulation

1. What types of code-switching are used by the host in the *B-cak Show* JTV episode “Dodit Mulyanto Segmen 5”?
2. How frequently does the host use code-switching in this video?

C. Objectives of study

1. To understand code-switching that used by host in the video of Indonesian local television program of B-Cak show JTV
2. To identify the frequency of code-switching used by the host in the video.

D. Research methodology

This research is a qualitative study that employs a sociolinguistic approach based on Poplack's theory (1980:230), which divides code-switching into three types: (1) inter-sentential switching, (2) tag-switching, and (3) intra-sentential switching. The data were collected by watching the video more than twenty times, then identifying and taking notes on the utterances of the hosts, Bung Sukir and Bung Sukur. Finally, the data were analyzed and categorized according to the types and frequency of code-switching.

E. Terms and Definitions

To avoid confusion in this paper, several key terms are defined as follows:

1. Code-switching

Poplack (1980:208) defines code-switching as "*the alternation of two languages within a single discourse, sentence, or constituent.*"

Different researchers have proposed different classifications of code-switching. According to Poplack (1980:230), there are three types of code-switching: inter-sentential switching, tag-switching, and intra-sentential switching.

- **Inter-sentential switching** occurs between sentences, where the switch takes place at a clause or sentence boundary, and each clause or sentence is in a different language.
- **Tag-switching** occurs when a tag phrase or discourse marker from one language is inserted into an utterance that is otherwise entirely in another language.
- **Intra-sentential switching** occurs within a single clause or sentence boundary, where elements of different languages are mixed within the same sentence.

2. B-cak show

B-cak Show is a comedy program that aired on JTV, a local television channel in the province of East Java, Indonesia. *B-cak* is an abbreviation of *Berita Kocak*, which means “funny news” in English. The announcers or hosts of this program are eccentric comedians, Bung Sukir and Bung Sukur, who are characterized by their frizzy wigs. They present the news in a humorous way. This program was broadcast from 2008 to 2016 on JTV. The broadcasting coverage of JTV reaches most areas of East Java Province.

F. Research finding and discussion

In this section, the discussion is divided into two subtopics: (1) the analysis of code-switching and (2) the frequency of code-switching.

1. Analysis code switching

There are some types of code switching happened in the video of “B_cak Show JTV Eps Dodit Mulyanto Seg 5”. All of code switching can be seen in this table:

a. Conversation of the first host named Bung sukir

There are some types of code-switching we found in conversation of the first host on B-cak show named Bung Sukir

information:

1. The word with **bold** is English
2. the word with underline is Javanese
3. the normal sentence is Indonesian
4. the sentence with *italic* is meanings

No	Sentence/utterance	Type of code-switching
1	Iki acting toh? Terima kasih pemirsa anda masih di B-cak show. <i>(is it just acting? Thank you all you still stay tune on the B-cak show)</i>	Inter-sentential switching (<u>java</u> - indo)
2	Gini loh, <u>wong nek wes resi mendek.</u> <i>(so, a person who has mastered would be humble)</i>	Tag-switching (indo- <u>java</u>)

3	Kurang ajar <u>opo ngono cek</u> terharu. (<i>damn, what else.. in order to be touched</i>)	Intra-sentential switching (<u>indo-java</u>)
4	<u>Ra opo wes</u> terserah ungkap-ungkap <u>no jenengku sopo</u> terserah. (<i>no problem up to you say what is my real name it is up to you. </i>)	Intra-sentential switching (<u>java-indo</u>)

From the table above, we are introduced to four sentences which is taken from utterances of the host named Bung sukir. They contains elements of code-switching as following:

1. In Sentence (1), the host, Bung Sukir, greets the audience after speaking Javanese in a conversation with the other host. He then switches to Indonesian when addressing the audience. This instance is classified as inter-sentential code-switching because the switch occurs between two different sentences: the first utterance in Javanese is followed by an interrogative sentence in Indonesian.

2. In the sentence (2) is categorized as type of tag-switching because there is a Indonesian tag phrase “gini loh” which it can mean “like this or so” in English, then it is followed by a Javanese clause.

3. In the sentence (3) is categorized as a intra-sentential switching because the switching from Indonesian into Javanese happens within a sentence.

4. In the sentence (4) is the same type as in the sentence (3). The intra-sentential switching happens within a sentence. In other hand, the host as a Javanese man speak his mother tongue by switching into Indonesian in some phrases.

b. Conversation of the second host named Bung sukur

There are some types of code-switching we found in conversation of the first host on B-cak show named Bung Sukur:

No	Sentence/utterance	Type of code-switching
1	<u>Marunu takonano.</u> baca apa itu? (<i>then ask him. what are you reading?</i>)	Inter-sentential switching (<u>java-indo</u>)

2	Komik Antara Jawa dan Eropa Story and concept by Dodit Mulyanto. (<i>comic book "Antara Jawa dan Eropa" Story and concept by Dodit Mulyanto</i>)	Intra-sentential switching (indo- eng)
3	<u>Loh yo gak Jenenge</u> kita berdo'a bersama-sama semoga kita langgeng. (<i>no that is named we're wishing together hopefully we last</i>)	Intra-sentential switching (<u>java</u> -indo)
4	<u>Ngarit iku ono les'e yo?</u> bukannya itu bakat alam (<i>there is a course for ngarit/cutting grass for cattle? isn't it a natural talent</i>)	Inter-sentential switching (<u>java</u> -indo)
5	Terakhir itu dia jadi nganu, <u>Ngapur sesek.</u> (<i>The last he'd be, ngapur sesek/painting bamboo wall</i>)	Tag-switching (indo- <u>java</u>)
6	Ini komik bergambar gitu ya? <u>Lah iki komik gak nok gambare dodit iki kan.</u> (<i>This is comic/book with picture right? This guy Dhodit is a comic/stand-up comedian with no picture</i>)	Inter-sentential switching (indo- <u>java</u>)
7	<u>Nang kene dadi bung sukir,</u> Nah ini jelaskan. (<i>here he acts as Mr. Sukir, tell him</i>)	Tag-switching (<u>java</u> -indo)
8	<u>Paling gak sing yoopo ngunu loh..</u> Tanpa bung sukir itu saya mungkin tidak jadi. (<i>at least what is like.. without Mr. Sukir i couldn't be like this</i>)	Inter-sentential switching (<u>java</u> -indo)

Frequency of the code-switching

This is quantity of types of code-switchings that occurred in the first host "Bung sukir" and the second host "Bung sukur".

Frequency of types of code-switching		
Intra-sentential	Tag-switching	Inter-sentential
4	3	5
Overall Quantity of Types		12

F. Conclusion

In conclusion, as we know, code-switching cannot be separated from our daily life, as shown in the *B-cak Show*, where we found code-switching in the utterances of the hosts. The code-switching used by the hosts of *B-cak Show* JTV is a common phenomenon. There are some factors that might influence code-switching. One of them is the attitudinal factor, seen from the background of the hosts, Bung Sukir and Bung Sukur, who both come from the same ethnic group, Javanese. Another factor is the educational background, which reflects their ability to speak multiple languages, since both hosts are educated people.

In addition, the analysis revealed that there is code-switching in the utterances of both hosts. There are code-switches from Javanese into Indonesian, and vice versa. There are also code-switches from Indonesian into English. On the other hand, there are twelve instances of code-switching used by both hosts in the video. The quantity by type is as follows: four instances of intra-sentential switching, three instances of tag-switching, and five instances of inter-sentential switching. Thus, the total number of code-switching instances is twelve.

In the final explanation, the point is that code-switching has spread into many aspects of life, especially in television programs such as the Indonesian local program *B-cak Show* on JTV. It can be viewed as a form of globalization in the modern era. This study is expected to raise readers' awareness of such phenomena and serve as a reference for future research.

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AUDIO VISUAL

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